

Ballyrisode Fulacht Fia: A New Bronze Age Site on The Mizen

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In 2012 two archaeologists, Connie Kelleher and Áine Brosnan, while surveying maritime sites related to seventeenth century pirate activity on the Mizen, came across a previously undocumented site at Ballyrisode Beach. In 2018 Finola Finlay (the author) and Robert Harris stumbled across the same site (fig 1), which is now documented in the National Monuments records as site number CO147-091. While it is possible that the visible remains at the site represent cist burials, and there is a local tradition of pirate burials there (more on that below), its most likely function was that of a water-boiling site, known in Irish archaeology as a *fulacht fia*.

Fig 1: Ballyrisode Fulacht Fia.

In the sand at Ballyrisode Beach, immediately in front of the car park, is the remains of a stone trough. Three sides of a rectangle are defined by slabs laid on their sides in the sand, while two other upright slabs stand close by. It is immediately reminiscent of the well-known cooking site at Drombeg Stone Circle (figs 2 and 3), excavated by E M Fahy in the late 1950s.¹

What exactly is a fulacht fia? The name translates as a wild cooking place and it was coined to describe this kind of open air kitchen. In Britain they are known as Burnt Mounds. Typically, they consist of a trough surrounded by a mound of burnt stones. “The archaeological evidence suggests that troughs were lined with either timber planks, roundwood or wattlework, or else with stones. In rare occasions, troughs appear to be constructed of both timber and stone.”² The troughs are usually rectangular, but circular, oval and sub-rectangular shapes also occur.

The water in the trough was brought to a boil by dropping very hot stones into the trough, and therefore another feature of a fulacht fia is a hearth for heating the stones. Once the stones were used up (after heating and cooling one or more times they cracked and broke) they were tossed aside and over time a horseshoe-shaped mound of these burnt and shattered stones accumulated around the trough.

A stone-lined pit is occasionally found at these water-boiling sites, and these have been interpreted as roasting or dry-cooking hearths. The upright slabs at Ballyrisode may be what remains of such a feature.

Fig 2: Drombeg Fulacht Fia.

Fig 3: Drombeg fulacht fia, artist's impression (from Drombeg informational sign).

Our perception of these water-boiling sites as cooking places has also been heavily influenced by the experimental work carried out by Prof Michael J O’Kelly in the 1950s. In a 1954 paper⁸, O’Kelly relates the process he and his crew used at a fulacht fia in Ballyvourney (fig 4). The stones were heated in a fire and then dropped into the water. In this way 100 gallons could be brought to the boil in half an hour and they were able to cook a 10lb joint of mutton. They conducted a similar experiment in the roasting oven, finding the meat to be beautifully cooked under a dome of hot stones. [As an aside, as a student of O’Kelly’s, I remember him telling us about it and I can still see the obvious relish with which he described the juicy leg of mutton that emerged from the simmering trough after almost four hours (they used the 20 minutes to the pound and 20 left over formula) and how clean the meat was when unwrapped from its straw casing.]

In his excavations and experiments at Ballyvourney and Killeens, O’Kelly was able to estimate, by assessing the amount of stones that would be needed to cook and comparing that to the amount in the burnt mounds, that these sites had been used on multiple occasions and probably over many years, perhaps for generations.

The Ballyvourney and Killeens sites yielded dates of Early to Middle Bronze Age (c 2,000 to 1,200BC), the first fulacht fia to be dated. Subsequent excavations that could be dated using the radio carbon method yielded the same results, leading to the general conclusion by the 1980s that these water-boiling sites are Bronze Age. However, Hawkes, using a wide variety of archaeological techniques has come to the conclusion that they were in use both before and after that period.

The present study indicates that the predominant peak of burnt mound activity takes place in the Bronze Age. However, it is by no means confined to this period as examples exist from the Early Neolithic period through to the Early Iron Age. There is a notable decline in the use of pyrolithic technology during the Middle Iron Age while a critical review of the later Iron Age and medieval dating evidence suggests a complete absence.⁹

Hawkes proposes a model “of open-air communal feasting/food sharing hosted by small family groups, possibly as a medium for social bonding.” He points to the laborious and time-consuming nature of the cooking process, and posits that “burnt mounds may have represented significant places in which people engaged in different forms of social reproduction and the transfer of knowledge.”¹⁰

But what about a site like Ballyrisode, half buried in the sand? It turns out that there's a similar one in Co. Cork at Lispatrick on Courtmacsherry Bay, occasionally visible at low tide.¹¹ There is yet another one at Creadan in Co. Waterford, in which the trough was made of wood (fig 5). The report on the Creadan excavation included this information: "During the preliminary survey of the trough, a large area beyond the burnt stone spread was identified that contains a lot of shell, especially mussel shells, which may be the remains of a midden. Following excavation the remains of a possible shell midden composed entirely of small cockle shells, with small twigs and some bird or fish bones, was exposed beneath the burnt stone spread."¹²

The most helpful site to use as a comparison to Ballyrisode is probably the inter-tidal fulacht fia from Coney Island in Sligo. We are fortunate that the site was thoroughly analysed by James Bonsall and Marion Dowd of IT Sligo.¹³ Ciarán Davis found the site and also participated in the excavation and he kindly shared some of his photographs (fig 6).

Like Ballyrisode, the trough is stone-lined and full of sand from the movement of the tide, which covers it at high tide. It was dated using a charcoal layer beneath the floor slab, to the Late Bronze Age. The authors point out that it is impossible to tell whether the intertidal location of many such sites is a planned feature, or whether they were originally on dry land and have ended up in the intertidal zone due to erosion of shifting sea levels. However, at Coney Island it seemed clear that the fulacht fia had been deliberately constructed so that it filled with water at high tide and held that water for several hours afterwards.

Fig 5: Creadan Beach (Waterford) fulacht fia, trough made of wood. Photo © Mizen Archaeology.

Fig 6: Coney Island fulacht fia. Photo courtesy of Ciarán Davis.

The presence of a nearby midden, as in Creadan, indicated that this fulacht fia may indeed have been used to boil fish and shellfish in salt water - an efficient (and delicious) method of cooking seafood.

Careful searching in the vicinity of the Ballyrisode site failed to elicit any traces of a midden, which would have built up over time, with heavy use of the site. However, this is a very disturbed area, in which a car park was built in recent times, resulting in the moving of soil and rocks. Indeed, it is surprising that the traces of the fulacht fia are still clearly visible.

And what about those pirates? One of the reasons Dr Kelleher was searching in Ballyrisode was to document references to pirate activity in the area. On the other side of the Mizen is Canty's Cove, an area that in local tradition is associated with the Gaelic-Irish pirate Canty. He carried out his activities on the opposite side of the peninsula to William Hull and was active at a time when the English pirates were headquartered in Leamcon, Baltimore and Crookhaven; he appears to have remained in control within his own domain to at least 1629 but most probably into the 1640s. A set of steps are cut into the rock at Canty's Cove and "there are rock-cut platforms both immediate to the slipway and caves that most probably were used for landing goods, including fish and including illicit goods, no doubt."¹⁴

John Hawke collected the history and folklore of the Mizen, including stories about Canty. The following stories were told to John Hawke in 1995 by James Camier, and were handed down from his father, William Camier of Enaghoughter Townland: they therefore go back a good few generations:

... Boats from America and elsewhere came into Dunmanus Bay, the captains were invited into his house by Canty, were dazzled by a special grog, robbed and pushed through the north door over the cliff into the cove to the north. On one occasion Canty wanted to stop an invasion by some outsiders at Ballyrisode. He had a daughter, who did not want him to go and tried to stop him, so he shot her. He then crossed by land to Ballyrisode and by moonlight fought a battle on the first strand, which he won. Gravestones to the dead stood on the shore. One day, the son of a captain previously murdered by Canty, who was also a captain, on returning from America was invited in by Canty. But, knowing more than his father, when Canty asked him to step outside he pushed Canty over the cliff." James himself remembers some gravestones, but these have been covered by encroaching sand over recent years. (NB. Graves

existing on the second strand are of drowned sailors.)¹⁵

This information suggests that James Camier (or perhaps his father) attributed the stones on the 'second strand' to sailors' graves. These stones may be the small upright stones which lie close to the fulacht fia today: they certainly resemble grave markers in size and shape. In the context of a Bronze Age fulacht fia, however, they are likely to have been part of a hearth or roasting-pit.

The Ballyrisode inter-tidal fulacht fia, or water-boiling site, is a significant addition to the archaeology of West Cork, adding to our knowledge of Bronze Age social practices.

Acknowledgements: I am very grateful for valuable information and assistance received from Alan Hawkes, Ciarán Davis, Jerome Lordan, Connie Kelleher, Aine Brosnan, Simon Dowling, James Bonsall, Anthony Beese, Noel McDonagh, Robin and Sue Lewando, and Robert Harris.

Endnotes

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